

E5.2.1 Initial design of high precision smart telemetry for 6G optimization v1.0

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	6
List of Figures	6
List of Acronyms	7
1 Executive Summary	8
2 Introduction	9
2.1 Background	9
2.2 Motivation	9
2.3 Scope	9
2.4 Objectives	10
2.5 Overview of Telemetry in 6G Optimization and Holoportation	10
3 State of the Art	11
3.1 Evolution of Telemetry in Telecommunication Networks	11
3.2 Holoportation and Telemetry Integration	11
3.3 OpenTelemetry: A Cornerstone of Real-Time Monitoring	12
3.4 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Management	12
3.5 Innovative Proposals: MonB5G and GODAI	12
3.6 Comparative Analysis of Telemetry Architectures	12
4 Background	14
4.1 Foundations of 6G Telecommunication Networks	14
4.2 Telemetry's Role in Network Optimization	14
4.3 Holoportation Technology Landscape	14
4.4 Learnings from Existing Architectures	15
5 System Requirements Overview	16
5.1 Functional Requirements	16
5.1.1 Overview	16
5.1.2 Functional Requirements	16
5.1.3 Conclusion	17
5.2 Non-Functional Requirements	17
5.2.1 Overview	17
5.2.2 Non-functional requirements	17
5.2.3 Conclusion	18
6 Design Principles	19

6.1	Modular and Extensible Architecture.....	19
6.2	Compatibility with Existing Telemetry Architectures	19
6.3	Real-Time Monitoring and Proactive Intervention.....	19
6.4	Adaptability to Emerging Technologies	19
6.5	Holoportation Integration for Immersive Experiences.....	19
6.6	Scalability and Efficiency	20
6.7	Security-First Approach	20
6.8	Comprehensive Telemetry Data Management.....	20
7	System Architecture.....	21
7.1	Overview	21
7.2	Core Components.....	21
7.2.1	OpenTelemetry Integration	21
7.2.2	TM Forum Integration	24
7.2.3	Collectors	25
7.2.4	Services.....	27
7.3	Integration with Distributed MLOps Architecture	30
7.3.1	Modular Design	30
7.3.2	Independence from Service Layers	31
7.3.3	Collaboration in Distributed Learning	31
7.3.4	Performance Isolation through Distributed Learning	31
7.3.5	Containerized Solutions for Efficiency.....	31
7.3.6	Distributed Automated AI Pipelines.....	32
7.4	Integration with Orchestrator Solution	32
7.4.1	Overview	32
7.4.2	Resource Provision Module	33
7.4.3	Cloud Orchestrator	34
7.4.4	Artificial Intelligence Operations (AIOps).....	34
7.4.5	Automated Resource Provision.....	34
7.4.6	Application Management	34
7.4.7	Optimized Sinergy for Optimal Performance	34
7.4.8	Leveraging Common Aspects	35
7.4.9	Future Perspectives: Collaborative Efficiency	35
7.5	Workflow and Automation	35
7.5.1	Data Collection and Preprocessing.....	35
7.5.2	Feature Extraction	36
7.5.3	Model Training and Continuous Improvement.....	37
7.5.4	Inference and Real-time Decision Making.....	37

7.5.5	CI/CD Processes	38
7.6	Tooling and Technologies.....	38
7.6.1	Version Control Systems	39
7.6.2	Feature Store.....	39
7.6.3	Machine Learning Pipeline.....	39
7.6.4	Model Validation and Testing.....	40
7.6.5	Model Registry.....	40
7.6.6	Model Serving.....	40
7.6.7	Model Monitoring	41
7.7	Security and Compliance	41
7.7.1	Data Encryption	41
7.7.2	Access Control and Authentication	42
7.7.3	Audit Trails and Monitoring	42
7.7.4	Compliance Considerations	42
7.7.5	Threat Detection and Incident Response	43
7.7.6	Secure Telemetry Data Handling	43
7.8	Scalability and Performance	43
7.8.1	Handling Telemetry Data Volumes	43
7.8.2	Adaptive Resource Allocation	44
7.8.3	Edge-to-Cloud Continuum Optimization.....	44
7.8.4	Machine Learning Pipeline Efficiency	44
7.8.5	Performance Monitoring and Optimization	44
7.8.6	Scalability Testing.....	44
7.9	Conclusion.....	45
8	Conclusions	46

List of Tables

Table 1 Acronyms	7
Table 2. Functional Requirements	17
Table 3. Non-Functional Requierments	18
Table 4. Data Preprocessing Services.....	27
Table 5. Feature Extraction Services.	28
Table 6. Model Training Services.....	28
Table 7. Inference Services.....	29
Table 8. Alarm Services.	29
Table 9. Analytics Services.	29
Table 10. Proposal Version Control System	39
Table 11. Proposal Feature Store.	39
Table 12. Proposal Machine Learning Pipeline.	39
Table 13. Proposal Model Validation and Testing.....	40
Table 14. Proposal Model Registry.....	40
Table 15. Proposal Model Serving.....	40
Table 16. Proposal Model Monitoring.....	41
Table 17. Proposal Data Encryption	41
Table 18. Proposal Access Control and Authentication	42
Table 19. Proposal Audit Trails and Monitoring.....	42
Table 20. Proposal Compliance Considerations.	42
Table 21. Proposal Threat Detection and Incident Response.	43
Table 22. Proposal Secure Telemetry Data Handling	43

List of Figures

Figure 1. 6G evolution towards ML and AI.....	11
Figure 2. GODAI Network Architecture.....	13
Figure 3. Generic view of Mon5G slice structure.....	13
Figure 4. Holoportation Technology Landscape.....	14
Figure 5. OpenTelemetry Integration.....	21
Figure 6. Distributed Tracing	22
Figure 7. Metrics Collection	22
Figure 8. Logging Framework	23
Figure 9. Collectors Architecture.....	25
Figure 10. Automated AI Pipelines General Architecture	30
Figure 11. Integration with Orchestrator Solution	33
Figure 12. Data Collection and Preprocessing Workflow.....	36
Figure 13. Feature Extraction Workflow.	36
Figure 14. Model Training and Continuous Improvement Workflow	37
Figure 15. Inference and Real-time Decision Making Workflow.....	38
Figure 16. CI/CD Processes Workflow	38

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
6G	Sixth Generation (of communication networks)
QoE	Quality of Experience
SaaS	Software as a Service
API	Application Programming Interface
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
CoAP	Constrained Application Protocol
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
AIOps	Artificial Intelligence Operations
XML	Extensible Markup Language
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
TLS	Transport Layer Security
IDS	Intrusion Detection Systems
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management

Table 1 Acronyms

1 Executive Summary

Building upon the findings of previous deliverables, notably the "2.4 Report on requirements for high-precision smart telemetry" and "2.2 Report on requirements for AI Pipelines in the edge to cloud continuum," this paper presents a cutting-edge high-precision intelligent telemetry system. The research incorporates insights from various international community papers, creating a robust foundation that aligns with the latest advancements in the field.

The architecture of the presented system embraces OpenTelemetry integration and distributed MLOps principles, adhering to TM Forum standards. It leverages versatile collectors, ensuring adaptability across diverse network environments. With a primary focus on telemetry data processing, the architecture facilitates optimal data collection, processing, and analysis to meet the evolving demands of 6G networks.

The workflow and automation section outline a systematic approach, integrating automated AI channels and CI/CD processes. Covering data collection, preprocessing, feature extraction, model training, and real-time decision-making, the workflow emphasizes efficiency, accuracy, and continuous improvement. This comprehensive strategy ensures the intelligent processing of telemetry data.

Carefully selected tools and technologies align with the distributed MLOps architecture, emphasizing collaboration, model reliability, and efficient deployment. GitHub, Feast, Kubeflow, Deepchecks, and MLflow contribute to version control, feature storage, ML pipeline organization, model validation, and model registry.

Security and compliance measures are woven into the system architecture, addressing the imperative need to protect sensitive telemetry data and comply with regulatory standards. Encryption, access control, audit trails, and compliance considerations, including GDPR adherence, collectively form a robust security framework.

Scalability and performance considerations highlight the system's ability to handle substantial telemetry data volumes in dynamic 6G network environments. Building upon previous research, this system integrates horizontal and vertical scalability, adaptive resource allocation, and efficient edge-to-cloud continuum optimization to ensure optimal performance and adaptability.

In conclusion, this high-precision intelligent telemetry system is a forward-thinking solution, extending and integrating insights from previous deliverables and international papers. It stands as a leader in intelligent telemetry solutions, ready to navigate the complexities of future telecommunications landscapes, particularly in the context of 6G networks.

2 Introduction

The constant evolution of communication technologies is propelling us into the realm of 6G networks, which promise unprecedented connectivity, speed and intelligence. As we navigate this landscape, the complexities of optimising 6G networks require a sophisticated telemetry infrastructure that transcends conventional monitoring. This paper addresses the design challenge of creating a high-precision, intelligent telemetry system designed expressly for 6G optimisation. Rooted in the fundamental insights drawn from the "Report on Requirements for High Precision Smart Telemetry" and leveraging the rich web of telemetry architectures explored in related work, we aim to bridge theoretical foundations and practical implementations. This effort is further nuanced by considerations from the holoportation domain, where synchronisation, multi-sensor fusion, volumetric video coding, network management and platform state converge to redefine user-centric experiences.

2.1 Background

The context of our research lies in the convergence of advanced synchronisation mechanisms, multi-sensor fusion, volumetric video coding, network management and platform state considerations. The complexities involved underscore the need for a cohesive architecture that seamlessly orchestrates these elements. This demand for integration is not only driven by technological excellence but is also rooted in the quest for a holistic holoport experience.

2.2 Motivation

Motivated by the imperative for a telemetry system that not only observes but actively contributes to the optimisation of 6G networks, this paper aspires to translate theoretical concepts into practical solutions. Our motivation extends beyond conventional telemetry into the realms of real-time monitoring, analysis, and decision-making. OpenTelemetry integration, TM Forum's end-to-end performance management and insights from innovative approaches such as MonB5G and GODAI serve as a guide for our envisioned high-precision intelligent telemetry system.

2.3 Scope

Our approach extends beyond conventional telemetry, delving deeper into the domains of holoportation to ensure a comprehensive understanding of user-centric principles. Our goal is to design a telemetry infrastructure that not only optimises the 6G network but also contributes to exceptional quality of experience (QoE) in holoportation scenarios. Our effort encompasses intricate synchronisation orchestration, multi-sensor fusion, volumetric video coding, network management and platform state considerations.

2.4 Objectives

The main objectives guiding this document include:

- **Requirements Analysis:** Discover the unique characteristics and demands of 6G networks in the context of holoportation.
- **Architectural Proposal:** Present a comprehensive architectural framework that seamlessly integrates synchronisation, multi-sensor fusion, volumetric video coding, network management and platform state considerations.
- **OpenTelemetry Integration:** Explore the adaptability and granularity of OpenTelemetry within the specific context of 6G optimisation for holoportation.
- **TM Forum Integration:** Investigate the benefits of aligning with global standards and benchmarks through the integration of TM Forum services, especially in the holoportation domain.
- **Alarm and Analytics Services:** Develop monitoring mechanisms, real-time feedback, and advanced analytics to improve decision making, with a specific focus on holoportation scenarios.
- **KPI & Metrics Manager Services:** Ensure that performance metrics and KPIs are not only managed but also presented in a way that resonates with established objectives, addressing the unique needs of holoporting.

2.5 Overview of Telemetry in 6G Optimization and Holoportation

Before delving into the details of our proposed high-precision intelligent telemetry system, we provide a comprehensive overview of telemetry in the context of 6G optimisation, with special emphasis on holoportation scenarios. This includes a comparative analysis of existing telemetry architectures, extracting insights from centralised, distributed, and hierarchical models, adapting these considerations to the complexities of holoportation. These insights serve as a fundamental reference for our architectural design, laying the foundation for a telemetry system that meets the nuanced requirements of 6G networks in the immersive world of holoportation.

3 State of the Art

When navigating the landscape of high-precision intelligent telemetry for 6G optimisation, it is imperative to contextualise our efforts within the broader state of the art. This section summarises a review of contemporary developments, drawing insights from related literature and state-of-the-art telemetry architectures.

3.1 Evolution of Telemetry in Telecommunication Networks

Figure 1. 6G evolution towards ML and AI

The evolution of telemetry in telecommunication networks has traversed a trajectory from rudimentary monitoring to sophisticated and intelligent systems. The advent of 5G heralded a paradigm shift, introducing concepts such as edge computing, real-time analytics and distributed telemetry architectures. To understand the requirements of 6G optimisation, a retrospective analysis of the evolution of telemetry serves as a basis¹.

3.2 Holoportation and Telemetry Integration

A distinctive facet of our exploration lies in the integration of telemetry with holoportation technologies. As the literature in the field demonstrates, holoportation presents novel challenges, including synchronisation complexities, multi-sensor fusion, volumetric video coding, and platform state considerations. Therefore, the state-of-the-art calls for a telescopic view that encapsulates both the dynamism of 6G networks and the immersive experiences of holoportation.

¹ Kaur, Jasneet & Khan, M. Arif & Iftikhar, Mohsin & Imran, Muhammad & Haq, Qazi. (2021). Machine Learning Techniques for 5G and Beyond. IEEE Access. PP. 1-1. 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3051557.

3.3 OpenTelemetry: A Cornerstone of Real-Time Monitoring

The OpenTelemetry framework emerges as a cornerstone in the field of real-time monitoring. Its metrics and tracking APIs provide a granular understanding of system behaviour, which facilitates the identification of inefficiencies and bottlenecks. While the paper "Report on requirements for high-precision intelligent telemetry" provides fundamental insights into the utility of OpenTelemetry, our contribution lies in adapting and extending its capabilities specifically for the optimisation of 6G networks in the context of holoportation.

3.4 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Management

The integration of TM Forum's end-to-end performance management services introduces a layer of global standards and benchmarks. This alignment with industry best practices transcends speed and efficiency, emphasising the importance of consistency and reliability in 6G network optimisation. Our state-of-the-art review delves into the implications of this integration, discerning its potential impact in holoportation scenarios.

3.5 Innovative Proposals: MonB5G and GODAI

To enrich our understanding, we draw inspiration from innovative proposals such as MonB5G and GODAI. The MonB5G architecture offers a hierarchical framework for AI-driven network management, addressing scalability and efficiency challenges. Meanwhile, the GODAI framework presents a decoupled architecture for distributed systems, emphasising modularity and ease of integration. While we refrain from discussing these proposals directly, their architectural nuances serve as reference points for refining our own design of high-precision intelligent telemetry.

3.6 Comparative Analysis of Telemetry Architectures

A critical facet of the state of the art involves a comparative analysis of telemetry architectures. This includes centralised, distributed, and hierarchical models, each of which addresses specific use cases. Discerning the advantages and disadvantages of these architectures, especially in the context of 6G optimisation for holoportation, forms an integral part of our exploration of the state of the art.

By synthesising this knowledge, we position our work at the confluence of evolving telecommunications networks, holoportation technologies and contemporary telemetry architectures. Our goal is to contribute a nuanced perspective that navigates the complexities of 6G optimisation, informed by the rich tapestry of the state-of-the-art in telemetry and related domains.

Figure 2. GODAI Network Architecture

Figure 3. Generic view of MonB5G slice structure

4 Background

In the effort to establish an initial design for high-precision intelligent telemetry tailored to 6G optimisation, it is essential to establish a solid foundation. This section provides the fundamental elements and contextual background necessary for the subsequent stages of our work.

4.1 Foundations of 6G Telecommunication Networks

To understand the complexities of 6G optimisation, it is essential to have a solid understanding of the fundamental elements of 6G telecommunications networks. This encompasses the expected capabilities, architectural principles, and key performance indicators (KPIs) that define the landscape of next generation communication technologies. By laying these foundations, we establish the fundamental framework on which our design of high-precision intelligent telemetry will be built.

4.2 Telemetry's Role in Network Optimization

Telemetry has become a lynchpin in the optimisation of modern communication networks. Understanding its role in collecting, processing, and analysing data from network elements provides insight into the dynamics of real-time network management. As we embark on the design of intelligent telemetry for 6G, a thorough exploration of telemetry's contribution to network optimisation becomes a cornerstone.

4.3 Holoportation Technology Landscape

Figure 4. Holoportation Technology Landscape

Given our primary focus on integration, delving into the landscape of holoportation technologies becomes imperative. Synchronisation challenges, multi-sensor fusion, volumetric video coding complexities and platform state considerations demand in-depth exploration. By unravelling the complexities of holoportation, we set the stage for a seamless fusion with intelligent telemetry, creating an immersive and optimised 6G experience².

² Chen, D. Gao, C. H. Foh and H. Yan, "CFINT: Cluster Based Fast In-band Network-wide Telemetry in 6G-enabled Networks," 2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2022, pp. 1699-1704, doi: 10.1109/GCWkshps56602.2022.10008610.

4.4 Learnings from Existing Architectures

Leveraging insights from existing telemetry architectures, including OpenTelemetry, TM Forum end-to-end performance management, MonB5G³ and GODAI⁴, we distilled key learnings. Each architecture brings distinct elements that can inform the design of our high-precision intelligent telemetry. By drawing parallels and distinctions, we assimilate a knowledge base that guides our innovative approach in the context of 6G optimisation.

³ Kholidy, Hisham A. and Mohammed Abuzamak. "5G Network Management, Orchestration, and Architecture: A Practical Study of the MonB5G project." ArXiv abs/2212.13747 (2022): n. pag.

⁴ González Pacheco P. Real Time Control for Intelligent 6G Networks. 2023. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/2117/394841>. Accessed December 1, 2023.

5 System Requirements Overview

Based on the comprehensive system requirements described in the document "Requirements Report for High Precision Smart Telemetry", this section provides a concise overview of the key requirements to be met by our high precision smart telemetry design.

5.1 Functional Requirements

5.1.1 Overview

In this section, we detail the functional requirements for the proposed high-precision intelligent telemetry system tailored to the demands of 6G optimisation. The following tables describe the main functionalities required for the successful integration of telemetry with holoportation technologies.

5.1.2 Functional Requirements

Section	Requirements	Challenges
Advanced Data Collection	Real-time Data Processing, Integration with 6G Infrastructure	Processing noise in real-time, Ensuring constant bandwidth in varying network conditions
Data Aggregation and Pre-processing	Data Filtering, Data Compression	Distinguishing genuine data from noise, Applying lossless compression techniques
Real-time Data Transmission	Data Compression and Optimization, Dynamic Quality Adaptation	Balancing data size reduction with maintaining high fidelity, Adapting to dynamic network conditions
Edge Processing	Real-time Data Analysis and Refinement, Localized Data Storage	Implementing fast analysis algorithms, Ensuring fast storage and retrieval at the edge
Data Storage and Retrieval	High-capacity Storage, Data Integrity and Redundancy	Scalability, Ensuring data integrity and redundancy
Alerts and Notifications for Anomalies	User-configurable Alert Parameters, Multi-channel	Designing intuitive alert customization, Implementing robust multi-channel delivery

	Notification Delivery	
Integration with Other Services	Seamless Video Conferencing Integration, Cloud Service Linkages	Achieving synchronicity in video conferencing, Managing data transfer speeds in cloud integration
User Interface and Experience	Immersive 3D Interfaces, Customizability and User Profiles	Designing a natural 3D interface, Ensuring user-friendly customizability
Security and Compliance	End-to-End Encryption, User Authentication and Authorization	Implementing latency-free encryption, Establishing secure and user-friendly authentication

Table 2. Functional Requirements

5.1.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, the functional requirements lay the foundation for the high-precision intelligent telemetry system designed for holoportation over 6G networks. Each requirement addresses specific challenges in real-time data collection, processing, transmission, and user interaction, ensuring an immersive and seamless holoportation experience.

5.2 Non-Functional Requirements

5.2.1 Overview

In this section, we present the essential non-functional requirements for the proposed high-precision smart telemetry system designed to meet 6G optimisation demands. The following table describes the key features required for the successful integration of telemetry with holoportation technologies.

5.2.2 Non-functional requirements

Section	Requirements	Challenges
Scalability	User scalability, Load Balancing and Resource Allocation	Scaling for increasing users without performance degradation, Optimizing resource allocation for real-time holoportation with low latency
Interoperability	Device Interoperability, Integration with Third-Party Services	Working with diverse devices, Recognizing and adapting to different device capabilities for consistent performance, Seamless integration with third-party services

Modularity	Component-Based Design, Open APIs and Protocols	Building separate, interchangeable modules, Independent upgrades without affecting the entire system, Employing open APIs and protocols for third-party integrations
Quality Assessment	Real-time Performance Monitoring, User Experience Evaluation	Monitoring performance metrics in real-time, Continuous assessment and immediate issue resolution for holoportation quality, Systematically evaluating user experience for continuous improvement
Content Visual Quality	Holographic Rendering Fidelity, Resolution and Clarity	Rendering high fidelity 3D holographic content, Minimizing artefacts, pixelation, and discrepancies, Supporting high-resolution displays with clarity during fast movements

Table 3. Non-Functional Requierments

5.2.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, the non-functional requirements set the framework for the high-precision intelligent telemetry system designed to seamlessly integrate with holoportation over 6G networks. Each requirement addresses specific challenges related to scalability, interoperability, modularity, quality assessment and visual quality of content, ensuring an immersive, reliable and high quality holoportation experience.

6 Design Principles

6.1 Modular and Extensible Architecture

Our design adopts a modular and extensible architecture, structured as a Software as a Service (SaaS). Inspired by the principles of fundamental requirements documentation, this modularity ensures flexibility, facilitating the addition or replacement of components without disrupting the system. The objective is to support diverse telemetry requirements in the evolving 6G network landscape.

6.2 Compatibility with Existing Telemetry Architectures

A central design principle focuses on compatibility with existing telemetry architectures. Based on knowledge from the underlying documentation, our system integrates seamlessly with various communication protocols and supports vendor-specific data transformations. This compatibility extends to interoperability with other architectures, fostering collaboration and creating a unified telemetry ecosystem.

6.3 Real-Time Monitoring and Proactive Intervention

Leveraging OpenTelemetry's state-of-the-art capabilities, our design prioritises real-time monitoring. The system incorporates metrics and tracking APIs to provide a granular understanding of system behaviour. Proactive intervention mechanisms are incorporated to ensure optimal performance across the 6G network. The objective is to identify inefficiencies and anomalies quickly, avoiding potential degradation of user experience and network performance.

6.4 Adaptability to Emerging Technologies

In line with the principle of adaptability and future-proofing, our design is inherently adaptable to emerging technologies. The architecture accommodates rapid advances in distributed systems, artificial intelligence and holoportation technologies. By adopting a flexible and extensible approach, the system is well positioned to evolve with the changing requirements of 6G optimisation, reflecting the dynamic nature of the telecoms landscape.

6.5 Holoportation Integration for Immersive Experiences

A distinctive design principle revolves around the seamless integration of telemetry with holoportation technologies. Informed by the challenges described in the state of the art, our system addresses the complexities of synchronisation, multi-sensor fusion and volumetric video coding. The telemetry system is designed to enhance immersive holoportation experiences by optimising data processing and ensuring real-time interventions.

6.6 Scalability and Efficiency

Taking inspiration from the MonB5G and GODAI architectures, our system places a strong emphasis on scalability and efficiency. The design is adapted to the hierarchical framework proposed by MonB5G, ensuring scalability at different levels of the network. Cloud-native design principles, microservices and distributed machine learning techniques contribute to the efficiency of the system, allowing it to handle dynamic, large-scale 5G networks and beyond.

6.7 Security-First Approach

Security is paramount in our design principles, aligning with the Security Manager component in GODAI. Robust key management is integrated for secure communication between system nodes. Compliance with global standards and benchmarks, as demonstrated by TM Forum's end-to-end performance management, improves the overall security posture of the telemetry system. This security-first approach is critical to maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of telemetry data.

6.8 Comprehensive Telemetry Data Management

Our design principles prioritise efficient telemetry data management. The backend layer optimises data handling, ensuring a smooth flow from acquisition to analysis and storage. Detailed workflows associated with telemetry processes provide transparency and clarity in telemetry data management across the ecosystem.

In summary, these design principles set the guiding framework for the development of our highly accurate, intelligent telemetry system, ensuring alignment with the core principles.

7 System Architecture

7.1 Overview

Present a high-level overview of the system architecture, highlighting its main components and collaborative functionality. Emphasise the integration of OpenTelemetry, compliance with TM Forum standards and the role of compilers and services as vital architectural elements.

7.2 Core Components

7.2.1 OpenTelemetry Integration

The integration of OpenTelemetry is a fundamental element within the system architecture, providing a standardised and extensible framework for observability. OpenTelemetry plays a crucial role in improving visibility of system performance, facilitating efficient monitoring and enabling in-depth analysis of telemetry data. This sub-section elaborates on the key aspects of OpenTelemetry integration:

7.2.1.1 OpenTelemetry Integration

OpenTelemetry establishes a solid observability foundation by providing a unified approach to collecting distributed traces and metrics. The diagram below illustrates how OpenTelemetry forms the basis for comprehensive observability:

Figure 5. OpenTelemetry Integration

In this illustration:

- **Edge Device:** Represents the telemetry data generation point at the edge of the system, where devices collect and output data.
- **Telemetry Hub:** acts as an intermediate centre responsible for processing traces and metrics before sending them to the observability database. It includes components such as the tracking and metrics processor.
- **Cloud Service:** Represents cloud-based services that receive telemetry data, enabling centralised analysis and monitoring.

- **Observability Database:** A centralised database that stores tracking and metrics, enabling efficient retrieval and analysis.

7.2.1.2 Distributed Tracing

One of the key features of OpenTelemetry is its support for distributed tracking. This functionality is essential for visualising the flow of telemetry data between various components and services. The following diagram illustrates the concept of distributed tracking in action:

Figure 6. Distributed Tracing

In this simple diagram:

- **Trace Collector:** collects distributed tracks from the perimeter device and routes them to the tracking processor.
- **Trace Processor:** processes and analyses the traces, ensuring that the telemetry data is properly formatted and ready for storage in the observability database.
- **Trace Receiver:** On the cloud service side, this component receives processed traces, facilitating comprehensive visibility and analysis.

7.2.1.3 Metrics Collection

OpenTelemetry facilitates the collection of a variety of metrics, including system resource utilisation, application-specific metrics and custom-defined key performance indicators (KPIs). The architecture obtains information on the status and performance of individual components. The following diagram illustrates the metrics collection process:

Figure 7. Metrics Collection

In this simple diagram:

- **Metrics Collector:** captures a variety of metrics from the perimeter device, including performance metrics, resource usage, and other relevant data.
- **Metrics Processor:** Analyses and processes metrics data, ensuring consistency and compatibility with the observability database.
- **Metrics receiver:** On the cloud service side, this component receives processed metrics, enabling comprehensive analysis and visualisation.

7.2.1.4 Logging Framework

Logging plays a crucial role in capturing and analysing relevant system events and activities. The following updated diagram illustrates the logging framework within the OpenTelemetry integration:

Figure 8. Logging Framework

In this simple diagram:

- **Log Collector:** collects log data from the perimeter device and captures relevant events, errors and activities.
- **Log Processor:** processes and parses the log data, ensuring that it is correctly formatted and ready for storage in the observability database.
- **Log receiver:** on the cloud service side, this component receives processed log data, enabling in-depth analysis and troubleshooting.

7.2.1.5 Interoperability with Other Observability Tools

OpenTelemetry is designed to be interoperable with a wide range of observability tools, including tracking systems, metric backends and logging frameworks. This interoperability ensures flexibility in choosing the right set of tools for telemetry data analysis. The architecture leverages this compatibility to integrate with industry-leading observability platforms, enabling a customised approach to telemetry data visualisation and analysis.

In summary, the OpenTelemetry integration establishes a solid observability foundation within the system architecture. Through distributed tracking, metrics collection, cross-instrumentation and interoperability, OpenTelemetry enables the architecture to effectively monitor, analyse and optimise the processing of highly accurate, intelligent telemetry data.

7.2.2 TM Forum Integration

The integration of TM Forum within the system architecture is critical to providing a standardised and interoperable framework for end-to-end performance management services. Specifically leveraging TM Forum's end-to-end performance manager services, this component offers a comprehensive set of functionalities designed to optimise network performance monitoring, analysis and improvement. TM Forum integration is developed along several key dimensions:

7.2.2.1 End-to-End Performance Manager Services

TM Forum's end-to-end performance management services form the cornerstone of the architecture's performance management strategy. These services cover a range of capabilities, including:

- **Performance Monitoring and Measurement.** The system benefits from TM Forum's standardised performance monitoring, ensuring real-time visibility of network elements. Key performance indicators (KPIs) are constantly measured, providing information on the status and efficiency of the entire network infrastructure.
- **Fault and Alarm Management.** TM Forum services facilitate the proactive identification and resolution of faults and alarms within the network. Automated processes streamline fault detection, reduce downtime and improve overall system reliability.
- **Quality of Service (QoS) Management.** By adhering to TM Forum standards for QoS, the architecture ensures that services meet predefined performance levels. QoS management becomes a dynamic and adaptive process, responding to different network conditions and demands.
- **End-User Experience Management.** TM Forum's approach to end-user experience management allows the architecture to measure and optimise the quality of services from the user's perspective. This user-centric approach ensures that performance improvements are aligned with real user expectations.

7.2.2.2 Standardized Interfaces and APIs

To facilitate seamless communication and integration with TM Forum services, the architecture incorporates standardised interfaces and APIs. These interfaces comply with TM Forum specifications, promoting a plug-and-play ecosystem where different components and services can interact effortlessly. The use of standardised APIs enhances flexibility and ensures compatibility with the wider TM Forum ecosystem.

7.2.2.3 Interoperability and Future-Proofing

TM Forum integration is guided by a commitment to interoperability and future-proofing. By aligning with TM Forum frameworks, the architecture ensures compatibility with emerging technologies and evolving industry standards. This interoperable approach not only streamlines the integration of TM Forum services, but also positions the system to adapt to changing network landscapes and requirements.

In essence, the integration of TM Forum within the system architecture creates a standardised, interoperable and forward-looking approach to end-to-end performance management. Leveraging TM Forum's services, interfaces and commitment to industry

standards, the architecture is well equipped to deliver improved network performance and superior quality of service.

7.2.3 Collectors

In the high-precision intelligent telemetry ecosystem, collectors play a critical role in collecting, aggregating and forwarding telemetry data from various sources to downstream processing components. The architecture incorporates a variety of collectors, each designed to address the specific characteristics and requirements of different data formats, protocols and sources. The collectors ensure efficient and reliable ingestion of telemetry data, allowing downstream processing steps to run smoothly. The following collectors are integral components of the system:

Figure 9. Collectors Architecture.

7.2.3.1 Protocol-Specific Collectors

The protocol-specific collectors within the system are meticulously designed to handle telemetry data transmitted over different communication protocols, such as MQTT, CoAP, HTTP and others commonly used in network and IoT environments. These collectors are compliant with OpenTelemetry standards, ensuring compatibility and alignment with industry best practices. Key components within this category include:

- **Protocol Insight Engine:** Specialized components for decoding telemetry data based on specific communication protocols like MQTT, CoAP, and HTTP.

- **Telemetry Connection Manager:** Manages the establishment and maintenance of connections with devices transmitting telemetry data.
- **Data Spool Buffer:** Temporarily stores incoming data before processing to manage data spikes efficiently.

7.2.3.2 Data Format Collectors

Telemetry data typically exists in a variety of formats, including JSON, XML, CSV and proprietary formats specific to particular devices or applications. Data format collectors specialise in parsing and processing telemetry data in these various formats, standardising the information for further analysis. This category integrates seamlessly with OpenTelemetry, leveraging its support for multiple programming languages and instrumentation capabilities. Key components include:

- **Format Parsing Suite:** Components capable of parsing and interpreting telemetry data in various formats, such as JSON, XML, and CSV.
- **Data Format Normalizer:** Normalizes data from diverse formats into a unified structure.
- **Format Error Handler:** Manages errors that may arise during the parsing and normalization process.

7.2.3.3 Edge Collectors

In scenarios where telemetry data originates at the edge of the network, perimeter collectors play a crucial role. Optimised for resource-constrained environments, these collectors perform the initial processing of telemetry data locally before transmitting it to the central processing infrastructure. OpenTelemetry's lightweight agents are particularly suited to edge environments. Components in this category include:

- **Edge Data Optimizer:** Conducts initial processing of telemetry data at the edge to reduce the load on central processing components.
- **Edge Connection Orchestrator:** Manages communication with central collectors while considering edge-specific constraints.
- **Edge Data Cache:** Temporarily stores telemetry data before transmission.

7.2.3.4 Custom Collectors

The architecture supports customised collectors to accommodate unique telemetry sources or proprietary data streams. These collectors, tailored to specific requirements, enable seamless integration of telemetry data from specialised devices or applications. Leveraging the extensibility and flexibility of OpenTelemetry, organisations can develop custom instrumentation and collectors. Components in this category include:

- **Tailored Data Integrator:** Components designed for handling telemetry data from specialized devices or applications.
- **Custom Data Transformer:** Custom modules for transforming and preparing data for downstream processing.
- **Adaptation Configurator:** Enables users to configure and adapt the collector for specific use cases.

7.2.3.5 Centralized Collector Hub

All telemetry data collected converges into a centralised collection centre, which serves as a unified entry point for data into the system. This hub organises the flow of data from multiple collectors, performs initial validation and aggregation, and forwards processed data to downstream services. Centralised Collector Hub provides the control, monitoring and management of telemetry data across the architecture. Key components in this category include:

- **Telemetry Fusion Hub:** Aggregates telemetry data from various collectors and sources.
- **Data Integrity Validator:** Performs thorough validation and quality checks on incoming data.
- **Unified Data Distributor:** Distributes processed data to downstream processing components.

Together, these collectors, including OpenTelemetry and those compliant with TM Forum standards, form a resilient and scalable foundation for the telemetry data ingestion process. Their collective capabilities enable the system to handle heterogeneity of data sources and formats, ensuring that the architecture is well equipped to meet the demands of high-accuracy intelligent telemetry in dynamic and diverse environments.

7.2.4 Services

The services within the high-precision intelligent telemetry architecture are fundamental elements that organise the processing and analysis of telemetry data. Let us delve into the specific details of each service to understand their functions and contributions.

7.2.4.1 Data Preprocessing Services

The data pre-processing service serves as the initial step in telemetry data processing and focuses on cleaning, transforming and normalising the raw data. Key responsibilities include:

Feature	Description
Cleaning Raw Data	Identification and rectification of errors or inconsistencies in incoming telemetry data.
Transformation	Conversion of data into a standardized format suitable for downstream processing.
Normalization	Ensuring uniformity and consistency in the representation of data for coherent analysis.

Table 4. Data Preprocessing Services.

This service lays the foundation for reliable and consistent telemetry data, addressing data quality issues prior to subsequent processing steps.

7.2.4.2 Feature Extraction Services

The feature extraction service operates on pre-processed telemetry data, with the objective of identifying and extracting relevant features that improve the input for machine learning models. Its main functions include:

Feature	Description
Identification of Features	Analyzing data to identify key parameters and characteristics crucial for further analysis.
Extraction Process	Isolating and extracting features that contribute to the overall understanding of telemetry data.
Enhancing Data for Models	Preparing the data for effective model training by selecting informative features.

Table 5. Feature Extraction Services.

This service plays a key role in ensuring that the data input to machine learning models is rich in meaningful information, improving the models' ability to make accurate predictions.

7.2.4.3 Model Training Services

The Model Training Service uses machine learning algorithms to train predictive models based on historical telemetry data. Its operations include:

Feature	Description
Algorithm Selection	Choosing suitable machine learning algorithms based on the nature of telemetry data and the problem.
Training Data Preparation	Using historical data to train and optimize the performance of predictive models.
Continuous Improvement	Implementing continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD) practices for continual model enhancement.

Table 6. Model Training Services.

This service is essential for creating predictive models that can anticipate and adapt to changing conditions based on historical patterns.

7.2.4.4 Inference Services

The Inference Service is responsible for implementing machine learning models capable of making real-time predictions on incoming telemetry data. Its functions include:

Feature	Description
Real-time Decision Making	Applying pre-trained models to incoming data streams for immediate insights.
Integration with OpenTelemetry	Collaborating with OpenTelemetry for end-to-end performance management.
Feedback Loop	Providing insights from inference results to improve future model training.

Table 7. Inference Services.

This service enhances the architecture's ability to respond dynamically to changing conditions by making real-time decisions based on learned patterns.

7.2.4.5 Alarm Service

Dedicated alarm services operate proactively to identify and resolve faults and alarms within the network. These services include:

Feature	Description
Fault Detection	Early identification of faults or anomalies in the telemetry data.
Automated Resolution	Implementing automated processes to resolve detected issues.
Reduced Downtime	Minimizing downtime through swift fault resolution.

Table 8. Alarm Services.

Alarm services contribute significantly to the reliability and stability of the overall system by addressing problems promptly.

7.2.4.6 Analytics Services

Analysis services specialise in analysing telemetry data to obtain valuable information and optimise network performance. These services include:

Feature	Description
Performance Monitoring	Utilizing analytics to monitor the performance of network elements.
Quality of Service Optimization	Adhering to TM Forum standards for dynamic Quality of Service (QoS) management.
End-User Experience Enhancement	Focusing on improving the quality of services from the end-user's perspective.

Table 9. Analytics Services.

Analysis services contribute to data-driven decision making and continuous improvement of network performance by providing useful information.

7.3 Integration with Distributed MLOps Architecture

Figure 10. Automated AI Pipelines General Architecture

Building on the OpenTelemetry and TM Forum integration discussed in the previous sections, the system architecture seamlessly extends its capabilities to integrate with a distributed machine learning operations framework (MLOps). This strategic alignment is particularly significant within the evolving landscape of native 6G AI networks. Integration not only strengthens MLOps but also provides robust support for continuous integration (CI) and continuous delivery (CD). In this section we elaborate on key aspects of this integration⁵.

7.3.1 Modular Design

The modular design of the system architecture, as discussed in the OpenTelemetry integration section, is central to seamless integration with distributed MLOps. Organised into modular components that resemble a software-as-a-service (SaaS) solution, these components meticulously align with the principles inherent in the broader MLOps framework. This modular design not only ensures independent development, enhancement and scaling of MLOps layers, but also resonates with the basic principles of distributed learning. In the context of distributed learning scenarios within 6G networks, this modularity facilitates the training of AI models on multiple nodes, optimising resource utilisation and improving overall performance.

⁵ MLOps: Canalizaciones de automatización y entrega continua en el aprendizaje automático. (2023, 18 mayo). Google Cloud. <https://cloud.google.com/architecture/mlops-continuous-delivery-and-automation-pipelines-in-machine-learning?hl=es-419>

7.3.2 Independence from Service Layers

Continuing the theme of modularity, the system architecture extends this principle to maintain the independence of the service layers. This separation is crucial within distributed learning environments, as it allows the development and scaling of MLOps components without causing a direct impact on the service layers. This design philosophy ensures a high degree of flexibility and adaptability to evolving service requirements, providing independence in the evolution of MLOps functionalities.

In connection with the previous sections, the independence of the service layers allows for seamless integration with OpenTelemetry, ensuring that advances or changes in telemetry data collection and processing do not disrupt the evolution of MLOps functionalities. Similarly, TM Forum's end-to-end performance management services are unaffected and provide consistent monitoring and analysis capabilities.

7.3.3 Collaboration in Distributed Learning

The native AI operating segment, discussed in the OpenTelemetry section as a provider of specialised AI services to different segments of the network, is a testament to the collaborative nature of distributed learning. Instances such as URLLC, eMBB and mMTC collaborate efficiently, especially in distributed learning contexts. Their collaborative efforts extend to tasks such as resource allocation, where resources are shared across service sectors, ultimately improving the overall efficiency of the distributed MLOps architecture.

Distributed learning collaboration not only improves the efficiency of MLOps processes but also aligns perfectly with OpenTelemetry's ability to collect and analyse telemetry data across different network segments. TM Forum's standardised performance management further contributes to the collaborative effort by providing a unified approach to monitoring and analysing distributed IA services.

7.3.4 Performance Isolation through Distributed Learning

Distributed learning principles are employed within the embedded system architecture to maintain AI performance isolation. The system achieves this through well-defined retraining triggers, ensuring that any performance degradation in one segment instance minimally affects the others. This approach becomes indispensable in environments where different nodes exhibit varying performance and capabilities.

This concept of performance isolation relates directly to OpenTelemetry integration, where maintaining the accuracy of telemetry data collection is crucial without compromising the performance of other components. TM Forum standards compliance further contributes to maintaining overall performance and reliability.

7.3.5 Containerized Solutions for Efficiency

The emphasis on containerised solutions is a key element that ensures the efficiency of integration with distributed MLOps. As discussed in the OpenTelemetry section, containerisation decouples the execution of iterative processes, providing the agility to adapt to different demands across multiple nodes in the network. Containerisation significantly optimises resource utilisation, contributing to the overall efficiency and scalability of the distributed MLOps architecture.

This efficiency is aligned with the flexibility provided by OpenTelemetry and the interoperability facilitated by TM Forum, ensuring an agile and efficient integration process.

7.3.6 Distributed Automated AI Pipelines

The culmination of these integrative efforts results in the establishment of distributed automated AI pipelines. These pipelines traverse seamlessly from the network edge to the cloud, efficiently handling high-precision telemetry data, machine learning steps, training process automation, model training, evaluation, and continuous delivery process automation. Each interconnected stage harmoniously leverages the principles of distributed learning, thus improving the efficiency, scalability and adaptability of AI applications within the 6G context.

Going back to the previous sections, these distributed automated AI channels leverage OpenTelemetry's observability capabilities and TM Forum's end-to-end performance management services. This ensures a holistic approach to intelligent telemetry within the broader context of the MLOps framework.

In essence, integration with the distributed MLOps architecture positions the system for optimal performance. The robustness, adaptability and ability to meet the dynamic demands of modern network infrastructures, as discussed in the OpenTelemetry and TM Forum sections, are further enhanced in the context of distributed MLOps. This integrated approach is enriched by the inclusion of OpenTelemetry and TM Forum components, which provide an end-to-end solution for observability, performance management and intelligent telemetry within the context of 6G networks.

7.4 Integration with Orchestrator Solution

7.4.1 Overview

The orchestrator solution forms the fundamental framework for the proposed high-precision intelligent telemetry system, orchestrating the deployment and management of components at various edge locations. This architecture is meticulously designed to align perfectly with the intricate workflows and requirements of telemetry systems and MLOps.

This architecture includes key components, each of which plays a crucial role in ensuring the efficient deployment and operation of the entire system.

Figure 11. Integration with Orchestrator Solution

7.4.2 Resource Provision Module

The resource provisioning module acts as the cornerstone for orchestrating the provisioning and configuration of edge resources. Using an abstraction layer, it interfaces with a variety of vendors, ensuring flexibility in provisioning edge locations. The configuration process is automated through Ansible, making it easy to prepare edge resources and adapt to different edge configurations.

7.4.3 Cloud Orchestrator

At the heart of the system, the cloud orchestrator seamlessly manages the deployment of virtualised AR pipelines, virtual networks and associated elements. This orchestration solution operates with advanced software-defined networking (SDN) capabilities, providing a robust framework for deploying and managing virtual networks.

7.4.4 Artificial Intelligence Operations (AIOps)

In the dynamic landscape of the proposed intelligent telemetry system, AIOps occupies a central place. This component optimises system performance by leveraging real-time monitoring data. It employs various predictive intelligence techniques, including time series forecasting, machine learning models and deep learning models. Prometheus, an open source monitoring toolset, serves as the backbone for collecting essential performance data.

7.4.5 Automated Resource Provision

Automation is a key enabler in the proposed system. The automated resource provisioning module interfaces with various providers, using a common abstraction layer provided by Terraform. This ensures a simplified process for provisioning edge locations, spanning private data centres and different service providers.

7.4.6 Application Management

Efficient application management is facilitated through the OpenNebula⁶ Flow Engine. It implements and manages application workflows, ensuring that consistent sets of virtual machines serve specific purposes. The system features a marketplace with pre-configured application stacks, simplifying the deployment process and improving collaboration.

7.4.7 Optimized Synergy for Optimal Performance

- **Automated Resource Provision.** The orchestrator integrates seamlessly with the automated resource provisioning module of the telemetry system. This integration ensures optimal preparation of edge locations for telemetry and MLOps components, providing a common ground for optimised processes.
- **Application Management Synergy.** Within the application management domain, the orchestrator creates synergy by providing a unified marketplace for both telemetry and MLOps. This shared environment simplifies application deployment and operation, fostering collaboration and efficiency.
- **Harmony in AI Operations (AIOps).** A critical integration point is in the AIOps domain. The orchestrator's role in optimising system performance through real-time monitoring and proactive problem resolution benefits both telemetry data processing and machine learning model implementation. This convergence ensures efficient operations across the entire ecosystem.

⁶ OpenNebula Systems. Report on Requirements for Intelligent Zero-touch Network Management. October 2023. I2CAT.

7.4.8 Leveraging Common Aspects

The Orchestrator solution leverages commonalities that align perfectly with the distributed nature of telemetry systems and MLOps. It improves the efficiency of telemetry processing workflows and contributes to the scalability of the entire architecture.

7.4.9 Future Perspectives: Collaborative Efficiency

In conclusion, the Orchestrator solution, with its end-to-end architecture and seamless integration points with telemetry systems and MLOps, emerges as a central enabler for the proposed high-precision intelligent telemetry ecosystem. Its role in providing a unified approach fosters efficiency, collaboration and adaptability, laying the foundation for a robust and scalable system.

7.5 Workflow and Automation

The workflow and automation of the high-precision intelligent telemetry system plays a key role in the efficient processing of telemetry data, integration with AI models and continuous improvement. This section provides a complete breakdown of each stage of the workflow, along with the integration of automated AI channels and CI/CD processes.

7.5.1 Data Collection and Preprocessing

- **Data Cleaning.** During data cleansing, the system identifies and rectifies errors or inconsistencies in the incoming telemetry data. This is crucial to ensure the accuracy and reliability of subsequent analysis.
- **Transformation.** The transformation phase involves converting data into a standardised format suitable for further processing. This step ensures uniformity in the representation of the data, which alleviates the burden on subsequent stages.
- **Normalization.** Normalization is about ensuring uniformity and consistency in the representation of data for consistent analysis.

Figure 12. Data Collection and Preprocessing Workflow.

7.5.2 Feature Extraction

- **Identification of Features.** Feature identification involves analysing data to identify key parameters crucial for further analysis.
- **Extraction Process.** The extraction process isolates and extracts features that contribute to the overall understanding of the telemetry data.
- **Enhancing Data for Models.** Preparing data for effective model training involves selecting informative features.

Figure 13. Feature Extraction Workflow.

7.5.3 Model Training and Continuous Improvement

- **Algorithm Selection.** Choosing appropriate machine learning algorithms based on the nature of the telemetry data and the problem is critical.
- **Training Data Preparation.** The use of historical data to train and optimise the performance of predictive models involves several steps.
- **Continuous Improvement.** The implementation of continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD) practices for continuous model improvement is a dynamic process.

Figure 14. Model Training and Continuous Improvement Workflow

7.5.4 Inference and Real-time Decision Making

- **Real-time Decision Making.** Applying pre-trained models to incoming data streams to obtain immediate information involves complex processes.
- **Integration with OpenTelemetry.** Collaborating with OpenTelemetry for end-to-end performance management is a key aspect.
- **Feedback Loop.** Providing information from inference results to improve the training of future models creates a continuous feedback loop.

Figure 15. Inference and Real-time Decision Making Workflow.

7.5.5 CI/CD Processes

- **Automated Testing.** Implementing automated testing procedures to validate changes involves systematic checks at each stage.
- **Continuous Deployment.** Automating the deployment of new models or functions in the production environment requires a well-defined process.
- **Monitoring and Feedback.** It is essential to establish continuous monitoring mechanisms with feedback loops for further improvement.

Figure 16. CI/CD Processes Workflow.

7.6 Tooling and Technologies

This section provides comprehensive information on the fundamental tools and technologies for implementing the system architecture. The selection of these tools is based on their compatibility with the distributed MLOps architecture and their ability to optimise various aspects of the workflow.

7.6.1 Version Control Systems

Version control is essential for managing code, data and model artefacts. The system relies on robust version control systems to maintain traceability and reproducibility in telemetry data processing and model development.

Proposal Tool	Purpose	Integration
GitHub	GitHub serves as the primary version control system, facilitating collaborative development, branching, and pull requests.	The system leverages GitHub to version code, data, and model artifacts, ensuring a structured and organized approach to development.

Table 10. Proposal Version Control System

7.6.2 Feature Store

Feature Store plays a crucial role in organising and managing functions for machine learning models, improving reusability across different projects.

Proposal Tool	Purpose	Functionality
FEAST	Feast is employed as the Feature Store, offering functionalities for storing and managing features crucial for ML model training.	It supports both online and offline features, providing real-time access for model inference or training and batch scoring.

Table 11. Proposal Feature Store.

7.6.3 Machine Learning Pipeline

The machine learning (ML) pipeline organises the different stages of data processing, model training and validation.

Proposal Tool	Purpose	Key Features
Kubeflow	Kubeflow is a widely adopted open-source tool for creating ML pipelines, enabling scalable and portable workflows for building, training, and deploying models.	Kubeflow's scalability, portability, and composability align with the system's requirements, allowing for efficient orchestration of ML workflows.

Table 12. Proposal Machine Learning Pipeline.

7.6.4 Model Validation and Testing

Ensuring the reliability and quality of ML models is achieved through systematic validation and testing procedures.

Proposal Tool	Purpose	Flexibility
	Deepchecks is utilized for both model testing and ongoing monitoring of models after deployment.	Its flexibility, integration capabilities with various tools, and support for Hugging Face, Databricks, and Apache Airflow make it a valuable asset for the system.

Table 13. Proposal Model Validation and Testing.

7.6.5 Model Registry

A centralized Model Registry is essential for tracking and managing various model artifacts throughout the ML lifecycle.

Proposal Tool	Purpose	Integration
	MLflow serves as the Model Registry, offering APIs for model versioning, production-to-deployment transitions, and detailed model lineage.	Its seamless integration with Kubeflow ensures efficient tracking of model meta-data throughout the ML workflow.

Table 14. Proposal Model Registry.

7.6.6 Model Serving

Efficient deployment and serving of ML models are crucial for real-time decision-making in production environments.

Proposal Tool	Purpose	Versatility
	Cortex is employed for model serving, enabling automatic scaling of APIs to handle production workloads.	Cortex supports multiple frameworks, including TensorFlow, pyTorch, and scikit-learn, providing flexibility for deploying various types of models.

Table 15. Proposal Model Serving.

7.6.7 Model Monitoring

Continuous monitoring of ML models ensures optimal performance, detecting and addressing issues promptly.

Proposal Tool	Purpose	Versatility
	Deepchecks, along with Prometheus and Grafana, is utilized for real-time measurement tracking, visualization, and monitoring of both model quality and operational metrics.	This combination offers a comprehensive solution for model monitoring, covering aspects like outlier detection, model drift, request rate, and latency.

Table 16. Proposal Model Monitoring.

In summary, system tools and technologies are carefully selected to align with the distributed MLOps architecture, fostering collaboration, ensuring model reliability and facilitating efficient deployment and monitoring in production environments.

7.7 Security and Compliance

Security and compliance are fundamental aspects of the high-precision intelligent telemetry system, addressing the imperative need to protect sensitive telemetry data and align with regulatory standards. This section clarifies the meticulous security measures seamlessly integrated into the system architecture to maintain the confidentiality, integrity and availability of telemetry data.

7.7.1 Data Encryption

Safeguarding telemetry data begins with strong encryption mechanisms, which address both data at rest and data in transit. By adhering to industry standard encryption protocols, the system ensures that telemetry data remains protected during storage and while traversing the network.

Example	Technologies
Utilizing Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) for data at rest ensures that stored telemetry data remains secure. Additionally, Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocols are employed for secure communication, encrypting data during transit.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AES for data at rest • TLS for data in transit

Table 17. Proposal Data Encryption.

7.7.2 Access Control and Authentication

Ensuring that access to the system is judiciously controlled is a critical layer of defence. Role-based access control (RBAC) restricts access according to pre-defined roles, allowing only authorised users to interact with specific functionalities. The implementation of multi-factor authentication (MFA) adds an additional layer of security by requiring users to authenticate their identity through multiple verification methods.

Example	Technologies
Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) ensures that only authorized personnel, such as data scientists or administrators, have access to specific telemetry datasets. Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) requires users to authenticate via a combination of passwords, biometrics, or tokens.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• RBAC for access control• MFA for enhanced authentication

Table 18. Proposal Access Control and Authentication.

7.7.3 Audit Trails and Monitoring

The establishment of comprehensive audit trails and continuous monitoring systems is essential to maintain a vigilant posture against potential security threats. Audit trails meticulously document user activities, system changes and access attempts, providing a detailed record for retrospective analysis. At the same time, real-time monitoring systems detect and respond to any suspicious activity, ensuring rapid action against potential threats.

Example	Technologies
Detailed audit trails log user activities, system changes, and access attempts. Real-time monitoring tools, such as Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems, provide continuous oversight.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• SIEM systems for real-time monitoring• Log management tools for audit trails

Table 19. Proposal Audit Trails and Monitoring.

7.7.4 Compliance Considerations

Navigating the complex landscape of privacy and data protection regulations is achieved through a commitment to compliance. The system architecture is meticulously designed to comply with relevant regulations, such as GDPR, HIPAA or other applicable standards. Detailed documentation further supports these efforts, providing a transparent record of data handling practices, security measures and compliance procedures for potential regulatory audits.

Example	Technologies
The system aligns with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) by ensuring transparent data handling practices and providing users with control over their data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Documentation tools for clear records• GDPR compliance tools

Table 20. Proposal Compliance Considerations.

7.7.5 Threat Detection and Incident Response

The system's proactive defensive posture extends to automated threat detection and well-defined incident response plans. Automated tools continuously scan for potential security threats and anomalies in real time, enabling the system to respond quickly and mitigate security incidents. These incident response plans are a strategic plan to minimise the impact of security breaches.

Example	Technologies
Automated threat detection tools, like Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), continuously scan for anomalies. Incident response plans outline precise steps to mitigate and recover from security incidents.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• IDS for threat detection• Incident response tools for swift action

Table 21. Proposal Threat Detection and Incident Response.

7.7.6 Secure Telemetry Data Handling

The security of telemetry data is paramount at every stage of its lifecycle. Secure processing of telemetry data involves isolation measures to prevent unauthorised access, ensuring that sensitive data is handled within secure boundaries. Containerisation further enhances security by segregating telemetry data processing tasks in dedicated environments.

Example	Technologies
Containerization isolates telemetry data processing tasks into secure environments. Access controls and encryption further secure data handling stages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Containerization technologies (e.g., Docker, Kubernetes)• Access control mechanisms

Table 22. Proposal Secure Telemetry Data Handling.

In conclusion, the security and compliance measures built into the system architecture not only strengthen the protection of telemetry data, but also position the system as a standard bearer for regulatory compliance in the intricate landscape of smart telemetry.

7.8 Scalability and Performance

The ability to scale and adapt seamlessly to the dynamic demands of 6G networks is critical to the success of the high-precision intelligent telemetry system. This section clarifies the architectural strategies implemented to handle large volumes of telemetry data efficiently and optimise system performance.

7.8.1 Handling Telemetry Data Volumes

In the field of high-precision telemetry, the volume of data generated can be substantial. The system addresses this challenge through a combination of horizontal and vertical scalability. Horizontal scalability, achieved by implementing modular components, facilitates the distribution of data processing tasks among multiple nodes. This parallel processing capability ensures that the system can effortlessly accommodate increasing volumes of telemetry data by horizontally scaling resources.

7.8.2 Adaptive Resource Allocation

Dynamic resource allocation is essential to meet the fluctuating demands of 6G networks. The system employs adaptive algorithms that intelligently allocate resources based on real-time telemetry data loads. This adaptive approach optimises resource utilisation, prevents bottlenecks during peak usage periods and ensures that the system maintains optimal performance levels across different workloads.

7.8.3 Edge-to-Cloud Continuum Optimization

Efficiency throughout the process from the edge to the cloud is achieved through meticulous optimisation strategies. The system is designed to prudently balance processing tasks between edge devices and cloud resources. This not only minimises latency for processing critical telemetry data, but also optimises the utilisation of cloud resources, resulting in a harmonious and efficient workflow throughout the process.

7.8.4 Machine Learning Pipeline Efficiency

Integrating distributed machine learning principles into the architecture improves the efficiency of AI applications. Containerised solutions decouple iterative processes, introducing agility to adapt to various demands on different nodes in the network. This decoupling not only streamlines the machine learning process, but also contributes to the overall efficiency and scalability of the distributed MLOps architecture.

7.8.5 Performance Monitoring and Optimization

Continuous monitoring of system performance is essential to identify bottlenecks and optimise resource usage. The architecture incorporates robust performance monitoring tools that track key performance indicators, enabling proactive optimisation measures. This iterative approach to improving performance ensures that the system maintains high levels of efficiency even in the face of changing network demands.

7.8.6 Scalability Testing

Rigorous scalability testing is carried out to validate the ability of the system to scale correctly under varying loads. This testing involves simulating scenarios with increased telemetry data volumes and dynamically changing network conditions. By subjecting the system to these simulated stress tests, its scalability limits are identified, allowing for pre-emptive optimisations and strategic capacity planning.

In essence, the scalability and performance measures built into the system architecture not only enable the efficient handling of large volumes of telemetry data, but also position the system as a robust and adaptable solution capable of meeting the intricate demands of 6G networks.

7.9 Conclusion

In summary, the presented system architecture is presented as a robust and adaptive solution, meticulously designed to meet the complex demands of high-precision intelligent telemetry in the context of 6G networks. Through a modular and distributed approach, the architecture integrates seamlessly with a distributed machine learning operations framework (MLOps), strategically aligning with distributed learning principles.

The emphasis on modularity enables independent development, enhancement and extension of MLOps layers and AI functionalities, ensuring flexibility and adaptability. The architecture independence of the service layers further contributes to their agility in evolving service requirements, a critical aspect in the dynamic 6G network landscape.

Distributed learning collaboration, demonstrated through specific instances serving different network segments, demonstrates the system's efficiency in resource allocation and highlights the collaborative prowess of the native AI operating segment. Performance isolation, achieved through distributed learning principles and containerised solutions, ensures that the system maintains high AI performance even in diverse and challenging network scenarios.

Containerised solutions play a key role in improving integration efficiency, decoupling iterative processes in machine learning pipelines and optimising resource utilisation. The culmination of these efforts results in distributed automated AI pipelines that span the entire continuum from edge to cloud, facilitating the efficient flow of telemetry data, machine learning steps, training processes and continuous delivery.

Going forward, the architecture's alignment with the principles of distributed MLOps positions it at the forefront of advances in telemetry and AI-native networking. The ability to handle large volumes of telemetry data, adapt to dynamic network demands and optimise performance underlines the system's readiness for the future evolution of 6G networks.

This forward-looking approach is further enriched with knowledge of the general MLOps framework, as well as specific tools and technologies recommended for implementing the distributed MLOps architecture. Leveraging knowledge from GODAI and 5GMON provides additional context, enhancing the understanding of the distributed MLOps landscape within the scope of this end-to-end system architecture.

In conclusion, the presented system architecture not only meets today's demands for highly accurate intelligent telemetry, but also lays a resilient foundation for the changing landscape of 6G networks, where seamless integration of native AI capabilities is paramount.

8 Conclusions

In this comprehensive exploration, we have delved into the design, implementation and strategic considerations of the high-precision intelligent telemetry system, positioning it as a cutting-edge solution tailored to the demands of 6G networks. Through a thorough examination of every facet, from architecture and workflow to tools, security and scalability, a coherent narrative emerges that highlights the robustness and adaptability of the system.

The architecture, a combination of OpenTelemetry integration, TM Forum standards and distributed MLOps principles, forms the backbone of the system. Its ability to collect, process and analyse telemetry data is complemented by a versatile range of collectors, promoting resilience and scalability across diverse network environments. Collaboration with distributed MLOps exemplifies a forward-thinking approach, ensuring support for evolving machine learning workflows.

Workflow and automation intricately organise the data processing and model development stages. The selected tools and technologies align perfectly with the distributed MLOps architecture, fostering collaboration, ensuring model reliability and facilitating efficient deployment and monitoring in production environments.

Security and compliance measures underscore the system's commitment to safeguarding sensitive telemetry data and complying with regulatory standards. Encryption, access control, audit trails and threat detection collectively establish a robust security posture, reinforcing system reliability and compliance with privacy regulations.

Scalability and performance considerations address the challenges posed by substantial telemetry data volumes in dynamic 6G network environments. Horizontal and vertical scalability, adaptive resource allocation and efficient continuous optimisation from edge to cloud reflect a system prepared for optimal performance and adaptability in the face of evolving network landscapes.

In essence, the high-precision intelligent telemetry system emerges not only as a response to the current demands of 6G networks, but also as a proactive solution designed to anticipate and navigate the complexities of future network infrastructures. The holistic approach to observability, standards compliance, security, scalability and performance optimisation positions the system as a cornerstone for the development of resilient and intelligent 6G ecosystems. As the telecom landscape evolves, this system is poised to meet the challenges, setting a precedent for innovation and excellence in intelligent telemetry solutions for years to come.